

1 Biosorption of heavy metals by microalgae: hazardous side effects for marine 2 organisms

3

4 **Keywords**

5 heavy metals, biosorption, microalgae, foraminifera, TEM investigations

6

7 **Abstract**

8 Biosorption is nowadays recommended as an ecological and environmentally friendly
9 alternative to remove metals from contaminated regions. Even in situ incubations of algae on
10 the seabed are conducted to investigate potential future ways of reducing metal
11 contamination. Our study investigated the negative effects on microorganisms when metal-
12 enriched algae are released into the marine environment. We cultured the microalgae
13 *Nannochloropsis oceanica* strain CCMP1779 with ¹³C/¹⁵N amended f/2 medium enriched with
14 four different metals (cadmium, copper, zinc, lead) and fed the resulting metal-enriched
15 microalgal biomass to *Ammonia confertitesta* (Rhizaria, Foraminifera) for two and six days.
16 Our study is the first study dealing with the interaction of biosorbed metals and the
17 metabolism of microorganisms. The effects of the uptake of these metal-enriched algae were
18 recorded by evaluating carbon and nitrogen uptake. Examinations using transmission electron
19 microscopy (TEM) were also carried out to better assess the condition of the foraminifera.
20 Foraminifera fed with metal-enriched microalgae show reduced carbon uptake and increased
21 nitrogen storage, indicating stress conditions. These observations suggest that trace metals
22 can induce stress which damages cellular metabolism. Interestingly, no cytological changes in
23 TEM analyses could be observed, which might be attributed to the relatively short incubation
24 time.

25

26

27 **1. Introduction**

28 1.1. Marine pollution and Bioremediation

29 At present, the contamination of surface and subsurface waters is a serious problem. The
30 pollution of the seas, especially coastal regions, is of global concern. Regarding inorganic
31 pollution, trace metals (TM) are the most listed pollutants, are non-biodegradable, persistent
32 and can have a negative impact on the ecosystem and humans (e.g., Kwaansa-Ansah et al.,
33 2019). Natural processes, such as volcanic eruptions, and human activities, such as mining,
34 agriculture, and wastewater discharge, can enrich the water body with TM (Gupte et al.,
35 2016). Trace metals can easily enter the food chain causing toxic effects on different organisms
36 (Pacheco et al., 2020). Recent studies show that elevated concentrations of TM can also be
37 found in the Arctic fjords in Svalbard, which clearly have anthropogenic origins (Zaborska et

38 al., 2020). The Arctic fjords exhibit moderate concentrations of Cu and Zn but are strongly
39 contaminated with Pb and Cd (Zaborska et al., 2020).

40 Due to the global contamination with TM in fresh- and seawater, it is crucial to identify
41 processes that can effectively remove these dissolved metals from wastewater and marine
42 environments. Traditional methods such as ion exchange, osmosis, evaporation,
43 electrochemical treatment, or precipitation require a great amount of energy and/or reagents,
44 making them costly (Salama et al., 2019). The recommended and eco-friendly alternative
45 method is phycoremediation or, in general, bioremediation. Trace metals such as Cu, Zn, Ni,
46 Mn, Fe and Co are essential micronutrients and, at low concentrations, contribute to healthy
47 growth in algae and plants in general, but exert toxic effects when present at higher
48 concentrations (Salama et al., 2019). In contrast, non-essential metals, such as Ag, Au, Al, Hg,
49 Ti, Cd, Pb and As, are toxic even at low concentrations and can limit or completely prevent the
50 cell activity of algae (Jais et al., 2017).

51 The general efficiency of algae to adsorb dissolved metals is very high. Both living and dead
52 algal cells can adsorb dissolved metals on their surface, but the efficiency of biosorption of
53 TMs is higher in living cells (Salama et al., 2019). Studies showed that green algae *Chlorella*
54 *minutissima* can adsorb 62, 74 and 84% of Zn, Cd and Cu from the wastewater (Yang et al.,
55 2015) and also the cyanobacteria *Spirulina* sp. can remove 91% of Cu present in municipal
56 wastewater (Al-Homaidan et al., 2015). A detailed list about the microalgae and their removal
57 efficiency in % is provided by Salama et al. (2019, table 3).

58

59 1.2. Effect of trace metals on marine microorganisms

60 Whether metals or TMs have negative effects on organisms depends on several factors. On
61 the one hand, not all TMs are equally harmful to every organism, and on the other hand, the
62 toxicity depends heavily on the concentration of the TMs (Martinez et al., 2023). Many TMs
63 are essential micronutrients for microorganisms at low concentrations and their survival is
64 dependent on these elements (Gadd, 1992). This study focuses on foraminifera, a group of
65 single-celled organisms, inhabiting all marine habitats (Sen Gupta, 2003). Because
66 foraminifera are highly sensitive to environmental changes, they can be utilized as indicators
67 for both fossil and recent environmental changes (Langer, 2008). Due to their abundance and
68 diversity, foraminifera are an important component in the marine carbon and nitrogen cycle
69 (van Lith et al., 2009). As they can made up to 84% of the biomass in some habitats, they
70 further represent an important part of the food chain and transport matter in the form of
71 energy to a higher trophic level (Lei et al., 2014).

72 In 2006, Ferraro et al. investigated 90 surface sediment samples from three different docks in
73 Naples Harbor. They found high levels of Ni, Pb, Zn and Hg (21, 270, 490 and 1.2 mg/kg) and
74 no living foraminifera in the most polluted dock. However, living foraminifera were collected
75 in another less polluted dock (Levante dock) with *Ammonia* being the dominant taxon. This
76 led to the suggestion that *Ammonia* may serve as a bioindicator of pollution (Ferraro et al.,
77 2006). Similar observations by other authors, such as Nigram (1984) and Samir and El-Din
78 (2001) have also concluded that certain foraminiferal taxa like *Ammonia* or *Quinqueloculina*,

79 are better adapted to higher concentrations of toxic metals than others. Rumolo et al. (2009)
80 specifically examined the metal content of the shell of *Ammonia* collected from polluted
81 harbour sediment in Naples. They demonstrated that based on the carbonate/seawater
82 distribution coefficient of heavy metals, the dissolved metal concentrations in the harbours of
83 Naples were 100 to 10,000 times higher than those measured in other uncontaminated
84 Mediterranean seawaters. In laboratory experiments examining the feeding behaviour of
85 foraminifera under significant increases in Pb, Zn or Cu concentrations in the medium, it was
86 shown that not all metals had a negative effect on the metabolism of foraminifera (Lintner et
87 al., 2021). Some metals, such as Cu, exhibited toxic effects at concentrations as low as 5 times
88 those found in natural seawater, while others, such as Pb, were not toxic to foraminifera even
89 after being enriched more than 500 times (Lintner et al., 2021). Zinc, however, has a positive
90 effect on foraminiferal metabolism at slightly elevated concentrations, but it also has a
91 harmful effect at higher levels. This pattern was also observed by Bubl et al., (2024) in the
92 symbiotic large benthic foraminifera *Heterostegina depressa*. Additionally, it was
93 demonstrated that Fe contributes positively to metabolic activity in this species, likely due to
94 the stimulation of obligate symbionts (Bubl et al., 2024). Due to this sensitivity to pollutants,
95 foraminifera are an ideal proxy for determining the level of pollution in the marine area (Malek
96 and Frontalini, 2024).

97 In our current study we aim to investigate whether metals such as Zn, Pb, Cu and Cd are toxic
98 to benthic foraminifera when ingested alongside their primary food source, microalgae. For
99 our experiments, we use *Ammonia* as, a very common genus of foraminifera in shallow marine
100 environments. However, this taxon often poses a problem when identifying at species level
101 due to its morphological diversity (Hayward et al., 2021). To accurately determine the species
102 examined in this study, additional genetic studies were conducted on several *Ammonia*
103 specimens to confirm their identity. Previous dissolved metal incubation experiments by
104 Schmidt et al. (2022) have demonstrated that Pb can be incorporated into the shell of
105 foraminifera, while Lintner et al. (2021) confirmed that elevated concentrations of Pb in
106 culture water do not exhibit toxicity to foraminifera. To resolve this intriguing controversy, we
107 hypothesize that dissolved metals like Pb may not be toxic to foraminifera because they are
108 incorporated into their shells and thus, are not concentrated in the cytoplasm. To test this
109 hypothesis, we enrich algae with metals through biosorption and offer them as the sole food
110 source to foraminifera. This method allows the metals to be absorbed directly into the
111 cytoplasm. The feeding behaviour was assessed using isotope labelling and cytological
112 analysis with transmission electron microscopy (TEM). As mentioned, many studies examined
113 how dissolved metals affect various organisms, their metabolism or their genetics. However,
114 to our knowledge, our study is the first to examine the interaction of biosorbed metals and
115 organisms and is intended to provide information about how the metabolism changes when
116 metal salts are unintentionally consumed together with the natural food source.

117

118 **2. Material and methods**

119 2.1. Study area and sediment sampling

120 The sediment samples containing *Ammonia* were collected from Kiel Fjord. The Kiel Fjord,
121 located in northern Germany, is heavily influenced by human activity, such as intensive traffic,
122 shipyard and harbour operations, leading to a high trace metal contamination especially in
123 the inner fjord (Haarich et al., 2003). This fjord extends approximately 9.5 km in a north-south
124 direction and is a part of the southwestern Kiel Bight in the Baltic Sea.

125 During a cruise on R.V. Alkor on September 28th, 2023, a Rumohr lot was taken near marine
126 harbour Kiel Wik (54.352650, 10.150129), and the top centimeter (fluffy layer) was carefully
127 removed using a syringe. This upper surface sediment was immediately covered with seawater
128 from the sampling site and sent to the Biogeosystem Modelling Lab of the ING PAN Research
129 Center in Kraków. There, the sediment was placed in a glass aquarium and covered with new
130 seawater from the sampling site to serve as a stock culture.

131

132 2.2. Culturing enriched microalgae

133 The microalgae (*Nannochloropsis oceanica* strain CCMP1779) used as food source for the
134 foraminifera were cultured in f/2 medium according to the method described by Guillard and
135 Ryther (1962) at the Stazione Zoologica Anton Dohrn (SZN) in Naples. To produce microalgal
136 biomass enriched in stable carbon and nitrogen isotopes, ^{13}C ($1.5 \text{ mmol L}^{-1} \text{ NaH}^{13}\text{CO}_3$) and ^{15}N
137 ($0.44 \text{ mmol L}^{-1} \text{ Na}^{15}\text{NO}_3$) were used instead of ^{12}C and ^{14}N to prepare the f/2 medium used for
138 microalgal culturing. Five separate cultures (one per each metal and a control without metals)
139 were set up. The microalgae cultures start with about 150 million cells (30 mL of full culture
140 at approximately 5 million cell/mL) added to 2L f/2 medium. Microalgae were then cultured
141 for about 10 days until reaching a density of about 10 million cell/mL, to get the best
142 compromise between a highly dense culture and strains still in exponential phase of their
143 growth.

144 Metals were added separately to four algal cultures as follows: $1 \mu\text{M}$ Cd (CdCl_2), $5 \mu\text{M}$ Cu
145 (CuSO_4), $5 \mu\text{M}$ Zn (ZnSO_4) or $10 \mu\text{M}$ Pb ($\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$). The fifth culture was incubated without
146 metals and serves as a control sample. *Nannochloropsis oceanica* CCMP1779 was cultured in
147 2L bottles within a temperature controlled cabinet (20°C) with a 12:12 dark:light cycle. The
148 bottles were connected to an aquarium pump to ensure mixing and gas exchanges. Once the
149 algae had grown to a high density in the medium, they were harvested by centrifugation
150 ($800 \text{ rpm}/10 \text{ min}$). To remove marine salts, the algal pellets were washed three times with
151 distilled water. Finally, the microalgal biomass was shock-frozen in liquid nitrogen and then
152 freeze-dried for 3 days at 0.180 mbar . Dead algae biomass will be used during this experiment,
153 to ensure stable concentration of isotopes in the algae itself. The absorption of dissolved
154 metals on the algae was examined using scanning electron microscopy with energy dispersive
155 spectrometry (SEM/EDS; instrument details provided at 2.5.) at the University of Vienna.

156

157 2.3. Determination of metal concentrations in the algae

158 The measurement was performed at the AGH-UST University of Kraków. An aliquot of 8 mg of
159 dry algae powder placed in a platinum crucible and completely dissolved using 5 mL of HNO_3

160 (65%) with few drops of HClO₄ (60%). The solution was dried out, dissolved again in hot HCl
161 and filled up to 10 mL. The concentration of TMs in the solution was determined with Atomic
162 Absorption Spectrometry (AAS) using a Thermo Scientific ICE 3500 AAS spectrometer. The
163 experimental detection limits were 0.01 ppm for Zn and Cd, 0.03 ppm for Cu and 0.07 ppm
164 for Pb.

165

166 2.4. Feeding experiments

167 The feeding experiments were carried out in crystallization dishes filled with sterile filtered
168 water from the sampling site. The sediment was washed over a 150 µm sieve, and only
169 *Ammonia* specimens with an intense, characteristic yellow-coloured cytoplasm were selected.
170 Individual foraminifera were then cleaned of adhering material using a brush, and 15
171 specimens each were placed in separate crystallization dishes. All experiments were set up in
172 triplicates.

173 *Ammonia* specimens were then incubated in separate triplets with the 5 different algae (5 mg
174 per dish) for two and six days. The two-day experiments can provide information about how
175 foraminifera behave during acclimatization stage and the 6-day experiments provide results
176 of what happens afterwards. The total number of incubated foraminifera was 15x3x2x5 =450
177 (number of individuals per dish x replicates x time points x different algae). After incubation,
178 the foraminifera were removed from the cultures and cleaned of the adhering algae. Sufficient
179 algae were still found in the dish after incubation, indicating a continuous supply of food to
180 the foraminifera throughout the experiment.

181 The cleaned foraminifera were briefly washed with distilled water and transferred into pre-
182 weighed Sn capsules. They were dried there for three days at room temperature before the
183 shell was dissolved with 5 µl HCl (4%). Finally, the foraminifera were dried at 50 °C for three
184 days, re-weighed and sent to the Stable Isotope Laboratory for Environmental Research
185 (SILVER) at the University of Vienna for measurements. Detailed instructions for calculating
186 food uptake during the experiment are provided in Lintner et al. (2020).

187 To test for significant effects of heavy metal algae on the activity of the foraminifera, two-way
188 ANOVAs were calculated with a level of significance set at p = 0.05 for the carbon and nitrogen
189 uptake. Statistical tests were performed using PAST 4.03 (Hammer et al., 2001). Statistical tests
190 were performed using R programming software (version 4.4.1) (R Core Team 2018) via
191 R Studio integrated development environment (version 2024.04.2+764). The following R
192 packages were used: *ggplot2*, *ggpmisc*, *plyr*.

193

194 2.5. Transmission- (TEM) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

195 In parallel to the isotope experiments, foraminifera were incubated for subsequent
196 morphological analyses using TEM. As described above, 5 foraminifera were added to each
197 microalgal sample totalling 25 individuals and incubated for 6 days. After incubation, all
198 individuals were removed from the culture and cleaned from adhering algae.

199 Additionally, freeze-dried microalgal biomass was investigated via TEM to ensure that the
200 microalgae retained their original shape after centrifugation and freeze-drying treatments,
201 and that cell lysis or other damages were negligible. For TEM observations, foraminifera were
202 fixed immediately after incubation, algae powder was first rehydrated in artificial seawater
203 (salinity of 35) for 24h. Fixation took place with 2.5% glutaraldehyde, 2% paraformaldehyde
204 buffered with 0.1M cacodylate containing 0.4M sucrose and 0.1M NaCl for 3 hours. Samples
205 containing foraminifera were then decalcified with 0.1M EDTA (in 0.1M cacodylate buffer),
206 whereas this step was omitted for microalgal samples. Samples were stained with 1% OsO₄
207 for 1 hour and gradually dehydrated with ethanol (30/70/100%) before being embedded in
208 LVR resin (low-viscosity intermediate resins). The thin sections are contrasted with 4%
209 neodymium (III) acetate hydrate and 3% lead citrate.

210 TEM Zeiss Libra 120 with bottom mount camera Sharp:eye TRS (2 × 2 k) was used for
211 cytological analysis. To evaluate the absorbance of dissolved metals on the algae, scanning
212 electron microscopy (JEOL IT300) coupled with energy disperse x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) was
213 employed. EDS in low vacuum mode was utilized with an EDAX AMETEK detector. Sixteen dot-
214 mappings per sample at 512 x 400 resolution and 200µs dwell time were performed to analyse
215 the chemical composition of the metal-enriched algae powder.

216

217 **3. Results and discussions**

218 3.1. Cytology of the used microalgae and their metal adsorption capacity

219 Microalgae grew successfully in the metal-enriched culture medium described above. TEM
220 imaging confirmed that the cell structure of the algae has been preserved (Fig. 1), indicating
221 that the algae powder represented an ideal food source for foraminifera. The dissolved metals
222 present in the culture medium have been sorbed by algae. The content of TMs in dry algae
223 used for the feeding experiment is provided in Table 1. Secondary electron microscopy
224 coupled with EDAX element mapping confirmed the precipitation of Pb on the algae surface
225 (supplementary material S1 / supplementary figure 1). The other metals were absorbed in a
226 too low concentration and therefore below the detection limit of the EDAX. The exact
227 concentration was measured using ICP-MS and is provided in Table 1. The tested algae showed
228 a high capacity to remove Pb (51%) and Cu (76%) from the culture medium but were less
229 efficient to remove Cd (0.7%) and Zn (1.7%). In general, the adsorption of dissolved metals in
230 algae varies among species, as reported and summarized in the review by Chugh et al., (2022).
231 The removal efficiency of Cu was reported to be 80-88% (Buayam et al., 2019; Saavedra et al.,
232 2018). For Cd, the removal efficiency strongly depends on the species and ranges between 17
233 and 86% (Borah et al., 2020; Shanab and Shalaby, 2012). Zinc can be removed from the
234 medium up to 91% (Saavedra et al., 2018) and Pb even up to 100% (El-Naggar et al., 2018).

235 In our study (Table 2), the alga *Nannochloropsis oceanica* showed the lowest adsorption
236 capacity for Cd with only 16.7 mg/kg which is equal to 0.7%. However, Cd is known to be toxic
237 to algae and has an inhibitory effect on growth (Shanab and Shalaby, 2012) and since Cd
238 adsorption is highly species dependent it can be assumed that *N. oceanica* is very sensitive to
239 this metal. Higher metal uptakes were found in the algae incubated with Zn (101.7 mg/kg),

240 but the removal efficiency of about 1.7% was much lower than reported from other species.
241 A possible explanation is, that Zn is essential for organisms at trace concentrations but can be
242 toxic at higher levels, leading to decreased algal growth (Chugh et al., 2022). Copper uptake
243 was found to be more significant than zinc uptake, although high Cu concentrations in the
244 water can lead to organelle impairments and increased activities of antioxidant enzymes in
245 algae (Cavalletti et al., 2022). Although, *N. oceanica* was able remove 76.3% of the dissolved
246 Cu from the solution which is in same range other studies reported from (Buayam et al., 2019;
247 Saavedra et al., 2018).

248 The highest content of metal was observed in the lead-treated microalgal sample (20516.8
249 mg/kg). The initial Pb concentration was twice (molar based) that of Cu or Zn but the Pb
250 content in dry algae powder was more than 20 times higher than Cu and even 200 times higher
251 than Zn. It is known from the literature that some algae can remove up to 100% of Pb from
252 their culture medium (El-Naggar et al., 2018). In our study we observed a removal capacity of
253 51.5% for *N. oceanica*. However, this extremely high content of Pb compared to other trace
254 metals in algae is an artefact of our culturing experiment: amendments of Pb salts to a culture
255 medium containing dissolved phosphates resulted in precipitation of highly insoluble Pb
256 phosphates. This mechanism is associated with the amount of metal sorption on algae. The
257 presence of Pb phosphate precipitates on the surface of dry algae was confirmed by SEM
258 imaging. The algae powder with the adsorbed metals was first rehydrated in water before it
259 was fed to the foraminifera to ensure that only the adsorbed salts were available to the
260 foraminifera and no crystal precipitates that were not bound to the algae. Due to the strong
261 chemical bond between the organic groups of the algae and the metals, it is not possible to
262 wash the adsorbed salts from the algae even after the algae have been rehydrated (Chugh et
263 al., 2022).

264

265

266 Fig. 1: TEM images of the rehydrated control algae. The thick outer cell wall and organelles are in good
267 conditions and represent a successful freeze drying, resulting in an optimal food source for the feeding
268 experiments. **A:** overview of several embedded algae cells. **B:** detail image of one algae cell with clearly visible
269 organelles.

270

271 Table 1: Trace metal content in algae cultured for the feeding experiment, standard deviation in brackets. The
272 reference sample consists of algae cultured in the absence of metal salts and all concentrations were below
273 detection limit.

Sample	Concentration of metal in culture medium	Concentration of metal in culture medium [mg/L]	Content metal per dry mass [mg/kg]	Dry mass algae [mg]	Aborbed amout of metal [mg]	% metal absorption
Pb-Algae	10 μ M	2.0720	20516.8 (1405.3)	52	1.0669	51.5
Cd-Algae	1 μ M	0.1124	16.7 (0.8)	50	0.0008	0.7
Cu-Algae	5 μ M	0.3177	989.1 (20.2)	49	0.0485	76.3
Zn-Algae	5 μ M	0.3269	101.7 (6.7)	56	0.0057	1.7

274

275 3.2. Cytology of the foraminifera

276 Using DNA barcoding, the obtained *Ammonia* sequences are identified as *A. confertitesta*
277 Zheng that branch with five other specimens collected from Japan, China, Denmark and
278 Germany. The grouping is supported by strong bootstrap value (81%) (more details are given
279 in the supplementary material S2 and supplementary figure 2).

280 Metals are precipitated on the algae through biosorption, sometimes in very high
281 concentrations as shown in Table 1. However, no difference, such as degraded organelles, was
282 observed in the cytology of the control sample compared to the metal-treated foraminifera.
283 Consumption of metal-enriched food did not result in immediate death of the foraminifera,
284 as they were still alive at the end of the incubation period and their cytoplasm was intact (Fig.
285 2). The presence of chloroplasts in the same individuals confirms that foraminifera indeed
286 ingested the metal-enriched microalgae and thus the precipitated metal salts. However,
287 accumulation of metal salts negatively influenced the metabolism of the foraminifera,
288 resulting in a reduced food uptake (Fig. 3) and a lower pC:pN ratio (Fig. 4).

289

290

291 Fig. 2: Cytology of the different foraminifera samples. Chloroplasts (c) in the cells are indicator for food uptake
292 during incubation without metal (control) enriched algae (A) as well as with metal (in this case Pb) treated
293 algae (B).

294

295 3.3. Effect of trace metals on the metabolism of foraminifera

296 Previous studies have established the utility of foraminifera as bioindicators for metal
297 pollution (e.g.: Ferraro et al., 2006; Frontalini et al., 2008; Martinez et al., 2023). Experimental
298 investigations with dissolved seawater enriched with dissolved metals have demonstrated
299 that heavy metals, notably Cu or Hg, can significantly impair foraminiferal metabolism,
300 potentially increasing to their mortality (Frontalini et al., 2018, Lintner et al., 2021, Schmidt et
301 al., 2021). The amount of carbon absorbed (pC, in ng/ mg dry cytoplasm) during the feeding
302 experiments is significantly dependent on the metal-enriched algae used ($p=0.003$, $df=4$).
303 Carbon uptake slightly increased ($p=0.078$) in the control group over time (Fig. 3a). During
304 two-day incubation experiments the foraminifera fed with algae without metal enrichment
305 (Control_2d) showed no significant different carbon uptake in comparison to metal-treated
306 ones (supplementary material S3 / supplementary table 1,2) except to those which were
307 incubated with Cd enriched algae ($p=0.017$). Furthermore, within foraminifera exposed to
308 metals no significant differences in the carbon uptake can be observed after two days.
309 Foraminifera incubated for 6 days without metals showed a significant higher carbon uptake
310 in comparison to all metal-treated specimens (Fig. 3a, supplementary material S3 /
311 supplementary table 1,2). Based on the mean values of the up taken carbon, only the control
312 group shows an increase between two and six days. In contrast, all metal-treated foraminifera
313 showed a decreasing carbon uptake after two to six days.

314 Like carbon uptake, the nitrogen absorbed (pN, in ng/ mg dry cytoplasm) during the feeding
315 experiments is significantly dependent on the metal-enriched algae used ($p=0.007$, $df=4$).
316 Tukey's pairwise test showed just a significant difference between the control group and
317 foraminifera incubated with the Cd algae (supplementary table 3) already after 2 days of
318 incubation ($p=0.016$). Based on the mean values presented in Figure 3b, a similar pattern with
319 time, as observed for carbon uptake, can be noted. Specifically, an increase in nitrogen uptake
320 is only observed in the control group. In contrast, all other foraminifera show a decrease in
321 food uptake between the three- and six-days experiment. However, due to the high variance
322 (high standard errors), these trends in nitrogen uptake could not be observed on a statistically
323 significant level ($p>0.05$, supplementary table 3).

324

325 Fig. 3: Uptake of the foraminifera *A. confertitesta* during the two and six-day incubation experiment with
 326 different metal-enriched algae. a) Carbon (pC) uptake and b) nitrogen (pN) uptake. Error bars show standard
 327 error of three replicates. See supplementary S3, supplementary table 2 for data.

328
 329

330 Correlation analysis of pC:pN ratio is given in Figure 4. All trendlines were extended to the
 331 intercept and the equation was calculated. The lowest slope (0.2387x) was calculated for the
 332 control group and all other metals showed a higher slope indicating a lower pC:pN ratio. The
 333 highest slope was calculated for Cd (0.7621x), followed by Cu (0.5886x), Pb (0.4795x) and Zn
 334 (0.4231x). The results clearly indicate that the presence of metals in the food source leads to
 335 a direct change in the C:N balancing in the cytoplasm. Decreasing pC:pN ratio (equivalent to
 336 higher slope) is a direct effect of higher incorporated amounts of nitrogen by constant level of
 337 carbon ingestion.

338 The Cd-spiked algae showed a very low efficiency (0.7%) in metal adsorption, but the highest
 339 change in the pC:pN ratio in foraminifera was observed, which indicates that this metal is one
 340 of the most harmful ones for foraminifera. Specimens which were fed with Cd-spiked algae
 341 were the only ones to show a significant ($p=0.016$) change (increase) of nitrogen uptake
 342 compared to the control sample. We hypothesize that this increase of nitrogen uptake is a
 343 direct function of increased stress protein production which was also observed and described
 344 by Frontalini et al. (2018), when they exposed foraminifera to various dissolved metals.

345 Zinc is an essential element for all living organisms. Past studies have shown that Zn in slightly
 346 elevated concentrations has a positive effect on the metabolism of foraminifera (Lintner et al.,
 347 2021; Bubl et al., 2024). However, if the dissolved Zn concentration increases above a certain
 348 threshold, the activity of the foraminifera decreases, and the metal has a harmful effect on
 349 their metabolism. In our study, the algae powder contained only a very small proportion of
 350 Zn, as only 1.7% of the metal was adsorbed on the algae. During a short incubation period of
 351 two days, no negative effect of Zn on the foraminifera could be observed. However, after 6
 352 days, the carbon intake of the foraminifera that were fed the Zn-spiked algae was significantly
 353 ($p=0.022$) lower than that of the control group, indicating a possible toxic effect over a longer
 354 period. The nitrogen uptake was not affected by the presence of zinc, which finally led to an
 355 increase of the pC:pN ratio.

356 Of all algae offered to foraminifera in this study, the Pb-spiked ones contained the highest
357 metal content, but the foraminifera do not seem to react to them any more negatively than
358 in comparison to other metal-enriched algae. Similar observations were made by Lintner et
359 al. (2021), where the culture water was enriched with 557 times the concentration of lead and
360 the incubated foraminifera showed no reduction in metabolism. Even obligate
361 photosymbionts in foraminifera do not appear to react negatively to the presence of lead
362 (Bubl et al., 2024). In our study, Pb, along with Zn, causes the lowest deviation in the pC:pN
363 ratio compared to the control group (Fig. 4), even though the proportion of adsorbed metal
364 salts was the highest here. These results once again suggest that Pb, both as a dissolved
365 element and as a salt, is not harmful to foraminifera.

366 It is currently not known which metabolic pathways are affected by metals in foraminifera.
367 Foraminifera incubated with increased Cu concentrations did not show any significant Cu
368 uptake in the shells (Schmidt et al., 2021). Similar observations were made by Lintner et al.
369 (2021) and Bubl et al., (2024). The metabolism of foraminifera incubated with elevated Cu
370 concentrations was significantly reduced and carbon uptake was zero after three days,
371 indicating a total deactivation of metabolic activities. The carbon uptake in our experiments
372 was also highly significantly ($p=0.001$) decreased after six days if Cu is adsorbed on the food
373 source. The nitrogen uptake was not affected by Cu-spiked algae, but the general trend of the
374 pC:pN ratio shows that Cu was one of the metals which influenced the foraminiferal
375 metabolism.

376 We can only speculate at this time how foraminifera cope with the trace-metals when
377 ingesting the metal enriched-algae. Microalgae are known to minimise the toxicity of metals
378 by chelating them with intracellular ligands such as metallothioneins and phytochelatin
379 (Balzano et al., 2020, Balzano and Sardo 2022). In case of foraminifera, an alternative
380 explanation could be that some of the metals assimilated by foraminifera are rapidly expelled.
381 The defence mechanisms against heavy metal-induced stress were first described by Frontalini
382 et al. (2018) reporting increased number of lipid droplets, mitochondrial degeneration, and
383 degradation vacuoles. However, we observed that nitrogen uptake was higher in the
384 foraminifera treated with metals compared to the control group (Fig. 3). This response may
385 be attributed to stress-induced lipid production, a phenomenon documented by Frontalini et
386 al. (2018), following the incubation of foraminifera in seawater enriched with dissolved
387 metals. Our study confirmed this hypothesis since the pC:pN trendline of all metal treated
388 foraminifera have a higher slope than the control samples, indicating a higher nitrogen
389 metabolism in foraminifera when they were exposed to metals. In subsequent studies, high-
390 resolution methods such as NanoSIMS (nanoscale secondary ion mass spectrometry) should
391 now be used to clarify whether and how many protein droplets being formed in the
392 foraminifera when they are exposed to metals. Additionally, this method can be used to clarify
393 if metals accumulate in the foraminifera (in special vacuoles) or whether they can be excreted
394 from the cytoplasm.

395
396

397 Fig. 4: Correlation between the taken-up amount of nitrogen (pN, in ng/mg) against carbon (pC, in ng/mg) for all
398 incubation experiments (triplicates). Numbers indicate incubation length (2 and 6 days). Grey shaded areas show
399 the confidence intervals (level 0.95) of the linear regressions. Foraminifera incubated without metals (control)
400 showed the highest slope, indicating the normal (high) ratio of pC:pN. All metal treated foraminifera have a lower
401 pC:pN ratio explained by a reduced carbon and increased nitrogen uptake during incubation.

402
403
404

405 4. Conclusions

406 In the present study we successfully cultured *Nannochloropsis oceanica* strain CCMP1779 with
407 different toxic dissolved metals and utilized the resulting metal contaminated biomass for
408 feeding of foraminifera. Our findings revealed that *N. oceanica* exhibited a significantly lower
409 uptake rate for Cd (0.7%) and Zn (1.7%) compared to Cu (76.3%) and Pb (51.5%). After 6 days
410 of incubation all metal treated foraminifera reduced their carbon-based metabolism in
411 contrast to the control sample. The consumption of metal-enriched food leading to a
412 noticeable increase in nitrogen uptake and therefore to a change in the pC:pN ratio. These
413 results show a high toxic effect of Cd-spiked algae on foraminifera. Cu-spiked algae were less

414 harmful than Cd-spiked, and Zn- and Pb-spiked algae showed the lowest negative effect on
415 the pC:pN ratio of the foraminifera. Although the precipitated metal salts reduced the
416 metabolism of the foraminifera, they were not immediately toxic since no significant changes
417 can be observed in short (2d) experiments. Our hypothesis is that *Ammonia* specimens fed
418 with these enriched algae digested them, but the adsorbed salts were recognized as harmful
419 and subsequently excreted. If the foraminifera were exposed to metal spiked algae for a longer
420 time the process of metal excretion might be too slow to reduce all metals and they start to
421 harm the foraminifera. However, this hypothesis requires further investigation through
422 additional studies.

423

424 Declaration of competing interest

425 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
426 relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

427

428 Acknowledgment

429 This research is part of the project No. UMO-2022/47/P/ST10/01013 co-funded by the
430 National Science Centre and the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation
431 programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement no. 945339. For the purpose
432 of Open Access, the author has applied a CC-BY public copyright licence to any Author
433 Accepted Manuscript (AAM) version arising from this submission.

434

435 5. References

436 Al-Homaidan, A. A., Alabdullatif, J. A., Al-Hazzani, A. A., Al-Ghanayem, A. A., & Alabbad, A. F. (2015).
437 Adsorptive removal of cadmium ions by *Spirulina platensis* dry biomass. *Saudi Journal of Biological*
438 *Sciences*, 22(6), 795-800.

439 Balzano, S., Sardo, A., Blasio, M., Chahine, T. B., Dell'Anno, F., Sansone, C., & Brunet, C. (2020).
440 Microalgal metallothioneins and phytochelatins and their potential use in bioremediation. *Frontiers*
441 *in Microbiology*, 11, 527494.

442 Balzano, S., & Sardo, A. (2022). Bioinformatic prediction of putative metallothioneins in non-ciliate
443 protists. *Biology Letters*, 18(4), 20220039.

444 Borah, D., Kennedy, B., Gopalakrishnan, S., Chithonirai, A., & Nooruddin, T. (2020). Bioremediation
445 and biomass production with the green microalga *Chlorococcum humicola* and textile mill effluent
446 (TE). *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences, India Section B: Biological Sciences*, 90, 415-
447 423.

448 Bubl, M., Heinz, P., Wanek, W., Schagerl, M., Hofmann, T., & Lintner, M. (2024). Impact of heavy
449 metals (Cu, Fe, Pb, Zn) on carbon and nitrogen uptake of the diatom-bearing benthic foraminifera
450 *Heterostegina depressa*. *Heliyon*.

451 Buayam, N., Davey, M. P., Smith, A. G., & Pumas, C. (2019). Effects of Copper and pH on the Growth
452 and Physiology of *Desmodesmus* sp. AARLG074. *Metabolites*, 9(5), 84.

453 Billah, M. M., Mustafa Kamal, A. H., Idris, M. H., & Ismail, J. (2017). Mangrove macroalgae as
454 biomonitors of heavy metal contamination in a tropical estuary, Malaysia. *Water, Air, & Soil Pollution*,
455 228(9), 347.

456 Cavalletti, E., Romano, G., Palma Esposito, F., Barra, L., Chiaiese, P., Balzano, S., & Sardo, A. (2022).
457 Copper effect on microalgae: Toxicity and bioremediation strategies. *Toxics*, 10(9), 527.

458 Chugh, M., Kumar, L., & Bharadvaja, N. (2020). Bioremediation of heavy metals: a step towards
459 environmental sustainability. In *India 2020: Environmental Challenges, Policies and Green Technology*
460 (Vol. 66, pp. 77-90). Imperial Publications Pvt. Ltd.

461 Chugh, M., Kumar, L., Shah, M. P., & Bharadvaja, N. (2022). Algal Bioremediation of heavy metals: An
462 insight into removal mechanisms, recovery of by-products, challenges, and future opportunities.
463 *Energy Nexus*, 7, 100129.

464 El-Naggar, N. E. A., Hamouda, R. A., Mousa, I. E., Abdel-Hamid, M. S., & Rabei, N. H. (2018).
465 Biosorption optimization, characterization, immobilization and application of *Gelidium amansii*
466 biomass for complete Pb²⁺ removal from aqueous solutions. *Scientific Reports*, 8(1), 13456.

467 Ferraro, L., Sprovieri, M., Alberico, I., Lirer, F., Prevedello, L., & Marsella, E. (2006). Benthic
468 foraminifera and heavy metals distribution: a case study from the Naples Harbour (Tyrrhenian Sea,
469 Southern Italy). *Environmental Pollution*, 142(2), 274-287.

470 Frontalini, F., Nardelli, M. P., Curzi, D., Martín-González, A., Sabbatini, A., Negri, A., ... & Bernhard, J.
471 M. (2018). Benthic foraminiferal ultrastructural alteration induced by heavy metals. *Marine*
472 *Micropaleontology*, 138, 83-89.

473 Frontalini, F., & Coccioni, R. (2008). Benthic foraminifera for heavy metal pollution monitoring: a case
474 study from the central Adriatic Sea coast of Italy. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*, 76(2), 404-
475 417.

476 Gadd, G. M. (1992). Metals and microorganisms: a problem of definition. *FEMS microbiology letters*,
477 100(1-3), 197-203.

478 Gouy, M., Guindon, S., Gascuel, O., 2010. SeaView version 4: a multiplatform graphical user interface
479 for sequence alignment and phylogenetic tree building. *Mol. Biol. Evol.* 27, 221–224.

480 Guindon, S., Dufayard, J.F., Lefort, V., Anisimova, M., Hordijk, W., Gascuel, O., 2010. New algoritMs
481 and methods to estimate maximum-likelihood phylogenies: assessing the performance of PhyML 3.0.
482 *Syst. Biol.* 59, 307–321.

483 Gupta, A., Joia, J., Sood, A., Sood, R., Sidhu, C., & Kaur, G. (2016). Microbes as potential tool for
484 remediation of heavy metals: a review. *J. Microb Biochem Technol*, 8(4), 364-372.

485 Guillard, R. and Ryther, J.: Studies of marina planktonic diatoms: I *Cyclotella nana* Hustedt. and
486 *Detonula confervacea* (CLEVE) Gran. *Can. J. Microbiol.*, 8, 229–239, 1962.

487 Haarich, M., Pohl, C., Leipe, T., Grünwald, K., Bachor, A., v.Weber, M., Petenati, T., Schröter-Kermani,
488 C., Jansen, W., and Bladt, A.: Anorganische Schadstoffe, in: *Meeresumwelt 1999–2002, Ostsee, Bund-*
489 *Länder-Messprogramm für die Meeresumwelt von Nord- und Ostsee*, Kiel, 167–194, 2003.

490 Hammer, Ø., Harper, D.A.T., Ryan, P.D. (2001). PAST: Paleontological statistics software package for
491 education and data analysis. *Palaeontologia Electronica* 4(1): 9pp.

492 Hayward, B. W., Holzmann, M., Pawlowski, J., Parker, J. H., Kaushik, T., Toyofuku, M. S., & Tsuchiya, M.
493 (2021). Molecular and morphological taxonomy of living *Ammonia* and related taxa (Foraminifera)
494 and their biogeography. *Micropaleontology*, 67.

495 Holzmann, M., Gooday, A. J., Siemensma, F., & Pawlowski, J. (2021). Freshwater and soil
496 foraminifera—a story of long-forgotten relatives. *Journal of Foraminiferal Research*, 51(4), 318-331.

497 Jais, N. M., Mohamed, R. M. S. R., Al-Gheethi, A. A., & Hashim, M. A. (2017). The dual roles of
498 phycoremediation of wet market wastewater for nutrients and heavy metals removal and microalgae
499 biomass production. *Clean Technologies and Environmental Policy*, 19, 37-52.

500 Kwaansa-Ansah, E. E., Nti, S. O., & Opoku, F. (2019). Heavy metals concentration and human health
501 risk assessment in seven commercial fish species from Asafo Market, Ghana. *Food science and*
502 *biotechnology*, 28(2), 569-579.

503 Langer, M. R. (2008). Assessing the contribution of foraminiferan protists to global ocean carbonate
504 production 1. *Journal of Eukaryotic Microbiology*, 55(3), 163-169.

505 Lefort, V., Longueville, J.E., Gascuel, O., 2017. SMS: Smart Model Selection in PhyML. *Mol. Biol. Evol.*
506 34, 2422–2424.

507 Lei, Y. L., Stumm, K., Wickham, S. A., & Berninger, U. G. (2014). Distributions and biomass of benthic
508 ciliates, foraminifera and amoeboid protists in marine, brackish, and freshwater sediments. *Journal*
509 *of Eukaryotic Microbiology*, 61(5), 493-508.

510 Lintner, M., Biedrawa, B., Wukovits, J., Wanek, W., & Heinz, P. (2020). Salinity-dependent algae
511 uptake and subsequent carbon and nitrogen metabolisms of two intertidal foraminifera (*Ammonia*
512 *tepida* and *Haynesina germanica*). *Biogeosciences*, 17(13), 3723-3732.

513 Lintner, M., Lintner, B., Wanek, W., Keul, N., von der Kammer, F., Hofmann, T., & Heinz, P. (2021).
514 Effects of heavy elements (Pb, Cu, Zn) on algal food uptake by *Elphidium excavatum* (Foraminifera).
515 *Heliyon*, 7(11).

516 Abd Malek, M. N., & Frontalini, F. (2024). Benthic foraminifera as bioindicators of marine pollution: A
517 bibliometric approach to unravel trends, patterns and perspectives. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 199,
518 115941.

519 Nigam, R. (1984). Living benthonic foraminifera in a tidal environment: Gulf of Khambhat (India).
520 *Marine Geology*, 58(3-4), 415-425.

521 Pacheco, D., Rocha, A. C., Pereira, L., & Verdelhos, T. (2020). Microalgae water bioremediation: trends
522 and hot topics. *Applied Sciences*, 10(5), 1886.

523 Pawlowski, J., 2000. Introduction to the molecular systematics of foraminifera. *Micropaleontology*
524 46, 1–12.

525 Pawlowski, J., Holzmann, M., 2014. A plea for DNA barcoding of foraminifera. *J. For. Res.* 44, 62–67.

526 Rumolo, P., Manta, D. S., Sprovieri, M., Coccioni, R., Ferraro, L., & Marsella, E. (2009). Heavy metals in
527 benthic foraminifera from the highly polluted sediments of the Naples harbour (Southern Tyrrhenian
528 Sea, Italy). *Science of the total environment*, 407(21), 5795-5802.

529 Salama, E. S., Roh, H. S., Dev, S., Khan, M. A., Abou-Shanab, R. A., Chang, S. W., & Jeon, B. H. (2019).
530 Algae as a green technology for heavy metals removal from various wastewater. *World Journal of*
531 *Microbiology and Biotechnology*, 35, 1-19.

532 Saavedra, R., Muñoz, R., Taboada, M. E., Vega, M., & Bolado, S. (2018). Comparative uptake study of
533 arsenic, boron, copper, manganese and zinc from water by different green microalgae. *Bioresource*
534 *Technology*, 263, 49-57.

535 Samir, A. M., & El-Din, A. B. (2001). Benthic foraminiferal assemblages and morphological
536 abnormalities as pollution proxies in two Egyptian bays. *Marine Micropaleontology*, 41(3-4), 193-227.

537 Schmidt, S., Hathorne, E. C., Schönfeld, J., & Garbe-Schönberg, D. (2022). Heavy metal uptake of
538 nearshore benthic foraminifera during multi-metal culturing experiments. *Biogeosciences*, 19(3),
539 629-664.

540 Sen Gupta, B. K., & Sen Gupta, B. K. (2003). Foraminifera in marginal marine environments. *Modern*
541 *foraminifera*, 141-159.

542 Shamim, S. (2018). Biosorption of heavy metals. *Biosorption*, 2, 21-49.

543 Shanab, S., Essa, A., & Shalaby, E. (2012). Bioremoval capacity of three heavy metals by some
544 microalgae species (Egyptian Isolates). *Plant signaling & behavior*, 7(3), 392-399.

545 Tan, W. H., Tair, R., Ali, S. A. M., Talibe, A., Sualin, F., & Payus, C. (2016). Distribution of heavy metals
546 in seawater and surface sediment in coastal area of Tuaran, Sabah. *Transactions on Science and*
547 *Technology*, 3(1-2), 114-122.

548 van Lith, Y., Langezaal, A. M., de Nooijer, L. J., & van der Zwaan, G. J. (2009). Benthic foraminiferal
549 effect on nitrogen and carbon cycling. *The Journal of Foraminiferal Research*, 39(2), 97-111.

550 Zaborska, A., Strzelewicz, A., Rudnicka, P., & Moskalik, M. (2020). Processes driving heavy metal
551 distribution in the seawater of an Arctic fjord (Hornsund, southern Spitsbergen). *Marine Pollution*
552 *Bulletin*, 161, 111719.

553 Yang, J., Cao, J., Xing, G., & Yuan, H. (2015). Lipid production combined with biosorption and
554 bioaccumulation of cadmium, copper, manganese and zinc by oleaginous microalgae *Chlorella*
555 *minutissima* UTEX2341. *Bioresource Technology*, 175, 537-544.

556 Zhang, A., Wang, L., Zhao, S., Yang, X., Zhao, Q., Zhang, X., & Yuan, X. (2017). Heavy metals in
557 seawater and sediments from the northern Liaodong Bay of China: Levels, distribution and potential
558 risks. *Regional Studies in Marine Science*, 11, 32-42.